

Current Problems Faced by Pregnant Women in Modern Medicine

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Abstract: *Injuries occur in 6-7% of pregnant women, and 4 out of 1000 cases require hospitalization. As the gestational age increases, the number of injuries increases. The largest proportion of cases are related to road accidents (road accidents) — more than half, and about 22% of injuries occur due to falls and physical violence. The most common injuries are burns, electric shocks, and penetrating wounds[1.3.6.7.]. Injuries during pregnancy are considered the main cause of death not related to obstetric problems, accounting for 46% of cases. Fetal mortality from severe injuries averages 61% and can reach 80% in the event of maternal shock.*

Keywords: *problems, women, modern medicine.*

Introduction

Injuries occur in 6-7% of pregnant women, and 4 out of 1000 cases require hospitalization. As the gestational age increases, the number of injuries increases. The largest proportion of cases are related to road accidents (road accidents) — more than half, and about 22% of injuries occur due to falls and physical violence. The most common injuries are burns, electric shocks, and penetrating wounds[1.3.6.7.]. Injuries during pregnancy are considered the main cause of death not related to obstetric problems, accounting for 46% of cases. Fetal mortality from severe injuries averages 61% and can reach 80% in the event of maternal shock. At the same time, there is no direct relationship between the severity of the injury and intrauterine fetal death. The greatest number of injuries is recorded in the third trimester, and among the complications most often occur placental abruption and premature birth[2.8.]. Injuries in pregnant women can lead to immediate consequences, such as uterine rupture, high maternal and fetal mortality, as well as long-term consequences, including premature birth and adverse perinatal outcomes. Premature termination of pregnancy after an accident occurs in 0.4% of cases before 20 weeks and in 3.5% of cases at a later stage[4.5.]. The frequency of adverse perinatal outcomes increases with shock, bleeding (including uterine bleeding), which may require Cesarean section. Some studies claim that injuries do not lead to negative consequences for the fetus, if the above-mentioned complications do not occur. However, even with mild injuries, the risk of perinatal mortality remains high in most studies. The consequences of traumatic brain injuries in pregnant women can vary greatly, and their prognosis is difficult to predict due to the increased risk of polytrauma. A ruptured bladder is one of the rare complications of pregnancy-related injuries.

Complications of pregnancy itself, such as eclampsia and amniotic fluid embolism, can make diagnosis and treatment of trauma in pregnant women difficult [8]. These complications may occur earlier or later than the injury [9]. There is disagreement about how the nature of the injury and the severity of the injury affect the incidence of placental abruption. Most injuries, especially those resulting from road accidents, falls, etc., are associated with a high risk of this complication, according to many researchers [10, 11]. The authors note that the outcome of the victims (mother and fetus) worsens with the severity of the injury. However, some people [12] argue that the importance of mechanical injuries in the WHO-

Described severe injuries in pregnant women who persevered in pregnancy and survived to term show that spontaneous miscarriage, placental abruption, and serious fetal injuries occur with minimal maternal injuries [13]. Therefore, the occurrence of miscarriage and placental abruption should be evaluated carefully. Polytrauma causes more severe consequences. However, even in difficult situations, pregnancy can be saved if appropriate measures are taken. Injuries to the spine and pelvis associated with a violation of their stability are the most dangerous.

A number of authors concluded that women who gave birth in the last period of trauma had worse pregnancy outcomes. Maternal and fetal fatalities were generally associated with internal organ damage, and fetal death or intrauterine death correlated with gestational age during delivery.

Such results can be explained by the fact that the pelvic framework does not protect the pregnant uterus throughout the entire pregnancy period. It should be noted that injuries resulting from polytrauma include traumatic brain injury, compression uncomplicated fractures of the vertebral bodies, fractures of the pelvis and limbs, and other injuries that affect the course of pregnancy that occurs after 3-5 years. Clinical examination revealed fixed spinal deformities, limited spinal function, and reflex syndromes of post-traumatic osteochondrosis of the lumbosacral spine. The question of whether to perform a Caesarean section after pelvic fractures remains controversial.

Some authors believe that healed wounds in a simple pregnancy are not the cause of a cesarean section. They emphasize the importance of developing standards and objective outcomes for natural delivery after pelvic fractures. Other studies show that pregnant women who have suffered concomitant traumatic injuries have high maternal (18.2%), perinatal (55.3%) mortality and impaired reproductive function. In women who have suffered post-traumatic changes in the spine and pelvis, pregnancy and childbirth are accompanied by a high rate of complications and the need for Cesarean section (62.5%). Falls account for a significant proportion of the causes of injuries in pregnant women.

In the United States, a study found that the highest number of falls occurs in women in the third trimester of pregnancy (79.3%). These falls are associated with gait instability caused by a shift in the center of gravity relative to the protruding abdomen, weakening of the pelvic ligaments and joints, and increased pressure in the pelvic area, which leads to impaired neuromuscular transmission. This injury is observed in women in the first trimester of 9.4%, and in women in the second trimester of 11.3%. Since falls are associated with an increased risk of preterm birth, placental abruption, hypoxia, and fetal distress, hospitalization with close monitoring of the mother and fetus is recommended, especially after serious falls. Road accidents often cause blunt force injuries to the body. It has been shown that airbags do not increase the probability of adverse outcomes of road accidents in pregnant women.

The same results were obtained in the study of placental abruption cases in pregnant women who were protected by airbags, but did not use them. The function of seat belts remains controversial. While there are descriptions of cases of traumatic uterine rupture as a result of seat belt pressure on the lower abdomen at the time of an accident, a number of authors believe that the consequences of accidents are safer when using them. When analyzing the results of road accidents involving 148 pregnant women, it was found that in seven cases the fetus died without maternal death.

Risk factors for fetal death included the mother's age, loss of consciousness during an accident, and pelvic injuries. Although uterine rupture is extremely life-threatening to the mother and fetus, it is very rare in blunt abdominal injuries. In addition, peritonitis, which is most often the cause of ruptured hollow organs, is a rare complication on this basis. Despite the frightening prospect, some researchers were able to preserve pregnancy in all 29 women who underwent surgery. Blunt abdominal trauma during pregnancy is also associated with rapid and long-term complications. Pregnant women should be closely monitored, even if they do not have immediate complications, such as premature birth and placental abruption, which occur with severe injuries. This is associated with the risk of developing these

complications later in life. Examination of pregnant women with blunt abdominal trauma should include computed tomography (CT) and ultrasound to make sure that there is no abdominal bleeding, no internal injuries, and there are indications for surgery.

Information about thermal injuries is limited. However, burns with an area of less than 10% of the body surface are not considered to affect the course of pregnancy, and their termination is usually associated with a history of spontaneous miscarriage. In most cases, after extensive deep burns, the outcome of pregnancy is poor: 85 % of women have miscarriages, stillbirths or premature births. In the reviewed literature, there is no data on the frequency of maternal mortality.

However, there are methods that can help both mother and child recover. A 19-year-old woman, 34 weeks pregnant, suffered a 32% body area burn accompanied by shock, according to some authors. On the third day, the patient came out of shock, and on the fifth day, she developed burn sepsis with pulmonary edema. Since the patient's condition required a Caesarean section, the child was discharged on the 46th day after intensive care in a satisfactory condition. After the operation, the patient was on artificial ventilation for five days, after which she was discharged on the 45th day. Her condition was satisfactory. Penetrating injuries are associated with the use of firearms or bladed weapons. Injuries that occur during pregnancy are important because of the high risk to the mother and fetus.

A special place is occupied by injuries of the pregnant uterus, characterized by high mortality of the mother and fetus. Damage to neighboring internal organs is detected in 38% of cases. The need to assess the condition of the mother and fetus, while preserving the life of the mother is of paramount importance, makes clinical decisions difficult. It is reported that the fetal head received a gunshot wound. At birth, the child was diagnosed with meningitis, encephalitis and intracranial hemorrhage. During craniotomy, the pool is removed from the area of the right lateral ventricle. The child survived, but his physical and mental development was significantly behind.

If a pregnant woman is injured, the main goal of the doctor should be a thorough assessment of the mother's condition. First of all, hemodynamics and the state of the respiratory tract should be diagnosed. Visual diagnostics should be performed immediately. However, controversy continues around clinical protocols, such as the effects of radiation exposure and risks to the fetus, the need for informed consent, the comparative informativeness of ultrasound, computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and the use of intravenous contrast agents. Ultrasound examination for blunt abdominals in pregnant women, according to many researchers, allows you to avoid CT or cystography, as well as avoid invasive diagnostic methods. The range of issues associated with performing a caesarean section remains a serious problem with blunt abdominal trauma.

There is no generally accepted advice. It should be used in severe conditions of the mother (if the viability of the fetus is not doubtful), in cases of fetal abnormalities, and in cases where the preservation of the fetus poses a threat to the permanent condition of the mother. However, no researchers have developed specific pathology models or appropriate C-section protocols. In the case of a traumatized pregnancy, the assessment should be comprehensive. Positive results of the Kleihauer-Betke test were similar in pregnant women with fetal and maternal bleeding, as well as in people with a lower risk of these complications, so using this test alone is not informative enough to diagnose bleeding. However, some authors see the following factors that may lead to an unfavorable prognosis of the outcome of pregnancy trauma: the third trimester of pregnancy, abdominal trauma with more than 2 points on the ISS scale (injury severity scale) and a positive Kleihauer-Betke test..

Mineral changes are one of many metabolic changes that occur during a physiological pregnancy. During the first trimester of pregnancy, there is a significant increase in daily urinary calcium excretion, as well as levels of markers remodeling of bone remodeling. This is due to the fact that total and ionized calcium, inorganic phosphorus, parathyroid hormone, and markers of bone formation and

resorption in pregnant women do not change significantly. regulations. Some studies indicate the development of transient osteoporosis in pregnant women. These studies note that the frequency of its occurrence is not adequately estimated. Obviously, these changes will increase the risk of injuries to the musculoskeletal system, which are most common as a result of road accidents and catatrauma. It is reported [7] that with the progression of pregnancy, approximately 25% of women who have been injured experience delayed consolidation of bone fragments and the formation of false joints. Understanding how injuries can affect perinatal performance and pregnancy outcome is especially important during pregnancy. Physiological changes that occur during pregnancy can both hide and highlight injuries that have already been inflicted. An obstetrician should be present during the entire course of treatment. From the 10th week of pregnancy, the cardiovascular system of women shows the following changes: the volume of plasma increases. In late pregnancy, plasma volume increases by 45% compared to baseline due to increased levels of estrogen, progesterone, renin, and aldosterone. Increased tubular sodium resorption results in the retention of an additional 6-8 liters of total body fluid. Hypervolemia can contribute to traumatic bleeding. A pregnant woman can lose up to 34% of her blood volume without severe signs of shock, which creates a false sense of security. Pregnancy leads to increased but compensated intravascular coagulation, which has its advantages and disadvantages. After injury, an increase in coagulation parameters can improve hemostasis, but during immobilization, the probability of thromboembolic complications increases, which requires constant monitoring of hemostasis parameters and anticoagulant therapy. An increase in the level of the diaphragm by four centimeters due to the mechanical pressure of the enlarged uterus is one of the factors affecting the state of the respiratory system. There were significant changes in the minute volume of ventilation, mainly due to a decrease in functional residual capacity, which leads to the fact that pregnant women do not tolerate apnea well. Contractions of motility, secretion, and absorption are all part of the state of the gastrointestinal tract. This is due to increased levels of progesterone and estrogen during pregnancy, as well as displacement of the esophageal sphincter to the chest and a decrease in its functional properties. Increased glomerular filtration and blood plasma flow in the kidneys reflect changes in the urinary system. Enlargement of the uterus leads to compression of the ureters and bladder, as well as to the expansion of the calico-pelvic system. From the fifth to the sixth week of pregnancy, changes in the hemodynamic function of the kidneys are observed; by the fifth and sixth months, they reach their peak and then stabilize. The pituitary gland of pregnant women increases by 35%, which can lead to necrosis of the anterior part of the gland and its functional insufficiency. Diuresis increases in the first trimester, returns to baseline values in the second trimester, and decreases by the end of pregnancy. However, the posterior pituitary gland may also undergo changes that may be temporary or permanent. A lack of aldosterone causes polyuria, which is often the first sign of this complication.

A significant role is played by factors of the immune status of pregnant women, about which there is a lot of debate. Sex steroid hormones during pregnancy affect the functional activity of white blood cells in two ways. They reduce the phagocytic activity of neutrophils and monocytes, and also stimulate the formation of reactive oxygen species. However, in a study of how pregnancy affects injury mortality, it was shown that when comparing groups of women of the same age and with equivalent injuries, the mortality rate in pregnant women was significantly lower than in women who did not have pregnancy. The authors suggested that this is due to the hormonal background.

However, there is an opinion that pregnancy does not increase mortality and complications after injury, but affects the nature of the injury. Some authors suggest caution when supporting post-trauma hemodynamics, saying: "early use of vasopressors in the presence of blunt-force hemorrhagic shock is preferable to resuscitation measures using crystalloids, which reduce mortality by 40%."

Although there are not many publications dealing with pregnancy injuries, even fewer studies study the effects of trauma on the mother and child. These include a study that found that women who have suffered trauma and are discharged from the hospital in good and viable condition are significantly more likely to give birth prematurely. The severity of the injury and the duration of pregnancy correlate. When analyzing 61 cases of trauma in pregnant women, of which 59% occurred in the third trimester, it was found that maternal hypotension and a decrease in fetal heart rate are unfavorable signs of fetal death later in life. It is shown that the immediate start of cardiographic monitoring is crucial for determining the viability of the fetus. Active resuscitation of the mother is also crucial. The pregnant woman should be on her left side so that she can avoid compression on the inferior vena cava, reduce venous return, and reduce the hypotension that accompanies it. When it comes to minor injuries during pregnancy, special attention should be paid to this issue.

It highlights the fact that conventional methods for assessing the condition of the mother and fetus, such as a general examination, the Kleihauer-Bertke test Kleihauer-Bertke and monitoring the condition of the fetus for at least four hours, cannot predict possible complications.

During pregnancy, new tissues and organs that perform hormonal functions are formed in a woman's body. These include decidual tissue, placenta, syncytiotrophoblast (outer layer), and cytotrophoblast (inner layer). The hormones of the hypothalamus (hypothalamic-like hormones: gonadotropin releasing hormone, corticotrophic releasing hormone, thyroid-stimulating releasing hormone, somatostatin) and pituitary gland are very similar to the hormones produced by the placenta. However, their place in this process has not yet been determined.

Women suffering from other diseases, as well as pregnancy-related complications, can increase the intensity of adaptive responses that do not meet physiological requirements, which can lead to a breakdown. There are few studies that study pregnancy hormones after injuries, but there are many studies that study hormones in pathological conditions. A decrease in placental lactogen and alpha-fetoprotein levels in pregnant women with hyperthyroidism indicates the development of fetoplacental insufficiency and can be used to assess the condition of the fetus in the third trimester of gestation.

In addition, determining the level of cortisol is a sensitive hormone test that can determine the likelihood of termination of pregnancy in the second and third trimesters of gestation. A system for assessing fetoplacental insufficiency in pregnant women and women in labor is proposed using the antenatal scale, which takes into account clinical, laboratory and anamnestic signs, as well as the perinatal scale for predicting intranatal fetal hypoxia.

The role of these indicators in assessing the impact of trauma on the fetus and the course of pregnancy should be clarified. These indicators are likely to be associated with a late-stage injury. Undoubtedly, such studies are necessary, since most women who have suffered non-fatal injuries terminate their pregnancy at this stage.

conclusion

Thus, injuries during pregnancy are a significant medical problem. Separate studies show that injuries that occur during pregnancy are increasing. Severe uterine trauma plays an important role in the development of unfavorable maternal and perinatal outcomes. There is a small amount of research on the effects of trauma on perinatal performance and pregnancy outcome, depending on the nature and severity of injuries. They often contain conflicting information. Data on changes in the hormonal status and morphology of the myometrium of pregnant women after mechanical trauma of the uterus are practically absent.

In some cases, recommendations for the instrumental diagnosis of traumatic injuries in pregnant women are also contradictory. In most countries (according to the selected sources), there are no generally

accepted protocols for the diagnosis and treatment of injuries in pregnant women, as well as comprehensive data on the etiology of injuries in pregnant women. The problem is complex, because its solution must involve all emergency medicine specialists, even if obstetric and gynecological aspects will dominate..

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